

Assessment of Agronomic and Physiological Traits in Bread Wheat Genotypes Under Soil Salinity Stress

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Abstract

High soil salinity is a common abiotic stress factor that seriously affects crop production, particularly in semi-arid regions of the world. In order to investigate the effect of soil salinity stress on agronomic and physiological traits of bread wheat genotypes, two field experiments were conducted in the 2014-2015 growing season at two different locations in a randomized complete block design (RCB) with three replications. The first study site was located at the Agricultural Research Center in Miandoab city (Soil EC: 7.1 dS m⁻¹), and the second study site was in the protected area of Rashakan Environmental Reserve (Soil EC: 8.2 dS m⁻¹). Both study sites were located in the West Azerbaijan Province, Iran. The experiment included 14 bread wheat genotypes, comprising seven commercial varieties and seven promising lines. Several physiological traits and yield components were measured, including chlorophyll content, grain weight, and harvest index. Soil salinity stress had a statistically significant effect on agronomic and physiological traits of wheat genotypes. All studied wheat traits in Rashkan showed a lower range compared to Miandoab. Among the studied cultivars, the cultivar Ofogh (1421 kg ha⁻¹) and among the studied genotypes, the genotype MS-89-13 (2038 kg ha⁻¹) showed the highest grain yield. Therefore, these results indicated that Ofogh and MS-89-13 have the potential to be cultivated in saline soils. The genotypes MS-89-8 and MS-89-10 showed lower yield under saline conditions.

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1. Introduction

Various biotic and abiotic environmental stresses limit the growth of plants in many regions of the world (Rahim et al., 2025). Among the abiotic stresses, salinity, as an abiotic stress, significantly damages plants worldwide, leading to a decline in agricultural outputs (Allel et al., 2018). Salt stress affects plant biochemical and physiological functioning, accumulating Na^+ and Cl^- ions, and affecting the development and quality of plants (Forni et al., 2017; Nehra et al., 2024; Sharaya et al., 2023). High soil salinity is one of the limiting factors for crop performance, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, where it is considered one of the most fundamental problems in the agricultural sector (Munns, 2002). In this context, with its hot and dry climate, Iran has more than half of its arable land (approximately 27 million hectares), which is composed of saline and sodic soils. Therefore, to use these soils and saline water resources optimally, increasing plants' salt tolerance and higher production capacity is an important improvement approach (Rezvani Moghaddam and Koocheki, 2001). Bread wheat has stronger salt tolerance, influenced by genetic, environmental, and physiological factors, and can be selectively selected (Bhutta and Hanif, 2010; Munns and Tester, 2008). The salt tolerance of wheat is relatively 6 dS m^{-1} (Colmer et al., 2006). Soil salinity at different levels reduces the growth of wheat plants by decreasing the growth of roots and stems (Jamal et al., 2011). As mentioned above, soil salinity stress affects wheat grain yield, plant traits, and all vegetative and reproductive traits. This stress accelerates the transition to the reproductive stage and the completion of the plant growth period (Ehtaiwesh and Rashed, 2020). Wheat under salinity stress can lead to a yield reduction of up to 45%, which significantly affects the number of grains per spike, thousand-grain weight, and grain yield in both tolerant and sensitive wheat cultivars (Ali et al., 2009; Hassan et al., 2015). Saadatian et al. (2012) also observed that with increasing salinity levels, the percentage and rate of germination, plant height, thousand-

grain weight, number of grains per spike, spike number, biological yield, and grain yield of wheat cultivars decreased. Another detrimental effect of increased salinity is accelerated leaf senescence (Lacerda et al., 2003). However, according to Kumar et al. (2003), chlorophyll degradation is less in more resistant plant species under soil salt stress. In West Azerbaijan Province, more than 100,000 hectares of irrigated wheat are cultivated. In most counties of this province, farmers do not get more yield from cultivating existing varieties due to the sensitivity of wheat varieties to salt stress caused by soil and water salinity. The area of the second-class lands of the province is more than 30,000 hectares, and salinity is 4 to 8 dS m^{-1} ; the third-class lands of the province are more than 60,000 hectares, and salinity is 8 to 16 dS m^{-1} . The dominant crop cultivated in these lands, due to environmental limiting factors, is winter wheat, and introducing genotypes tolerant to soil salinity is crucial for the sustainable use of these lands. Therefore, examining and studying its traits and determining their susceptibility in the growth path of the plant can help identify effective mechanisms for coping with salinity. This study aimed to investigate the impact of soil salinity stress on physiological characteristics and yield components in the final yield of grain wheat. In the context of these facts, this study screened wheat genotypes in semi-arid regions of Northwest Iran (West Azerbaijan Province) for soil salinity resistance. We hypothesized that soil salinity stress can alter morphological and physiological traits, potentially introducing a higher-yielding wheat genotype or cultivar for cold and arid regions.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study area

The field experiments were conducted at two study sites during 2014-2015. The first study site was located at the Agricultural Research Center Station of Miandoab, Iran ($46^{\circ}05'$ E longitude and $36^{\circ}00'$ N latitude), with an elevation of 1142 meters above sea level. The second study site was in the protected area of Rashakan Environmental

Reserve, which was located 30 km from Urmia city, Iran ($45^{\circ}19'$ E longitude and $37^{\circ}18'$ N latitude), with an elevation of 1267 meters above sea level. Both study sites were located

in the West Azerbaijan Province, Iran (Figure 1). The weather data and study site information are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Weather statistics at the experimental site

Months	Urmia (2014-2015)			Miandoab (2014-2015)		
	Temperature average ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Evaporation total (mm)	Precipitation total (mm)	Temperature average ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Evaporation total (mm)	Precipitation total (mm)
October	15.2	76.5	4.9	16.3	83.2	4.4
November	5.4	14.9	47.5	7.4	19.6	32.5
December	-0.2	0	68.4	4.6	0	52.7
January	2.5	0	13.5	2.7	0	4.2
February	1	0	56.4	4.9	0	34.5
March	2.1	0	20	0.6	0	13.7
April	8.1	65.9	41.2	10.9	77	25.4
May	13.6	141.9	33.3	15.7	156.7	28.5
June	21.1	228.2	2.7	24.8	246.8	0.4
Agust	23.9	276.9	4.6	26.3	307.1	1
September	26	316.5	0	26.9	379.1	0
November	22	289.2	2.1	24.1	321.3	0

Figure 1. The study area (first and second experimental sites) in West Azerbaijan Province, Iran

2.2. Experiment design and analysis methods

Before sowing, the soil samples were taken from a depth of 0-30 cm at both experimental sites, and the physical and chemical properties of the soil at the experimental sites were determined (Table 2). The soil particle size distribution, pH (1:2.5 soil: water), electrical conductivity (EC), and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) concentration were analyzed with

Bauyoucos (1954), McLean (1965), Black et al. (1983), and Allison and Moodie (1965), using conventional procedures, respectively. The soil organic carbon (SOC) content was determined by the Walkley-Black method (Walkley and Black, 1934). The Kjeldahl digestion and distillation method was employed to quantify total nitrogen (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982), whereas available phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and micronutrients (iron and zinc) were determined

by Olsen (1954), Carson (1975), and Lindsay and Norvell (1978) methods, respectively (Table 2). The soil analysis results of the first experimental site revealed that the soil had a silty clay texture, with an EC of 7.1 dS m^{-1} , and a pH of 9. The texture of the second experimental site was silty loam with an EC of 8.2 dS m^{-1} and a pH of 12 (Table 2). The soil organic carbon (SOC) contents of the first and second experimental sites were determined to

be 0.61% and 0.33%, respectively. The soil organic carbon (SOC) contents were considered low in both experimental sites. The water used for irrigation was also analysed in the laboratory (Table 2). The EC of irrigated water was normal and acceptable ($\text{EC} < 4.0 \text{ mmhos cm}^{-1}$) for wheat, with its pH (about 8) within the natural range in both experimental sites (Table 2).

Table 2. Soil physical and chemical properties, and chemical characteristics of irrigation water at the experimental sites

Study site	Soil		Water	
Miandoab	EC (dS m^{-1})	7.1	EC	1.8
	pH	9.0	pH	7.6
	K (mg kg^{-1})	180	Carbonate (CO_3^{2-})	0.0
	P (mg kg^{-1})	8.4	Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-)	8.4
	Fe (mg kg^{-1})	3.3	Chloride (Cl^-)	11.1
	Zn (mg kg^{-1})	0.51	Calcium (Ca^{++})	4.8
	Organic Carbon (SOC) (%)	0.61	Magnesium (Mg^{++})	5.5
	Total Nitrogen (TN) (%)	0.90	Sodium (Na^+)	10.8
	Sand (%)	15		
	Silt (%)	42		
	Clay (%)	43		
	Texture	SiC		
	Urmia	EC (dS m^{-1})	8.2	EC
pH		12	pH	8.00
K (mg kg^{-1})		230	Carbonate (CO_3^{2-})	0.0
P (mg kg^{-1})		9.1	Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-)	9.1
Fe (mg kg^{-1})		1.1	Chloride (Cl^-)	9.3
Zn (mg kg^{-1})		0.37	Calcium (Ca^{++})	5.1
Organic Carbon (SOC) (%)		0.33	Magnesium (Mg^{++})	4.6
Total Nitrogen (TN) (%)		0.60	Sodium (Na^+)	12.11
Sand (%)		28		
Silt (%)		39		
Clay (%)		33		
Texture		CL		

The experiment utilized a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The soil of the Miandoab experimental site (the first experimental site) was under the cultivation of sugar beet in the spring of 2014, while the soil of the protected area of Rashakan Environmental Reserve was left fallow in 2014 to allow for soil recovery. The soil of the first experimental site was irrigated and then plowed after harvesting the sugar beet seeds in early autumn. The wheat genotypes were sown using a grain seed drill at the Miandoab station (the first experimental site), while in the protected area of Rashakan, it was done manually in September. According

to the local standard, the seed density was set at 450 seeds m^{-2} (approximately 160 kg ha^{-1}).

The treatments under investigation consisted of 14 bread wheat genotypes, including the cultivars Alvand, Zarin, Pishgam, Urum, Zarrin, Mihan, Ofogh, and seven promising lines (MS-89- 4, MS-89- 7, MS-89- 8, MS-89- 10, MS-89- 11, MS-89- 12, MS-89- 13). The seeds were sown in the plots, encompassing a surface area of 4.8 m^2 and comprising six rows separated by 20 cm spacing. After sowing, irrigation was carried out in October to germinate and establish the seeds in the soil. A consistent basal application of phosphate and potassium was implemented across all

experimental plots, at rates of 100 kg ha⁻¹ Diammonium phosphate (HPO₄(NH₄)₂) and 80 kg ha⁻¹ Potassium sulfate (K₂SO₄), respectively. Urea fertilizer was applied at 160 kg ha⁻¹ in three stages: 20 kg ha⁻¹ of urea fertilizer simultaneously with land preparation and before sowing as a base fertilizer, 70 kg ha⁻¹ as a road fertilizer at the tillering stage (Zadoks scale 21), and 70 kg ha⁻¹ at the stage when the stem starts to elongate (Zadoks scale 30). After favorable environmental conditions became available in mid-April, chemical control against narrow-leaved and broad-leaved weeds was carried out using the herbicides 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) at a rate of 1500 cc ha⁻¹ and Puma Super (fenoxaprop-p-ethyl 69 g L⁻¹ + mefenpyr-diethyl 75 g L⁻¹) at a rate of 1 L ha⁻¹. The chlorophyll content of flag leaves was measured with a chlorophyll meter SPAD502 Plus, Minolta, Japan) at the flowering stage (Zadoks scale 61). Also, after wheat ripening, the traits spike weight, thousand-grain weight, number of grains per spike, grain weight per spike, as well as biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (HI) were calculated from the harvested samples using a sensitive balance and seed counter.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Combined analysis of variance over two locations and graphical representations of the results were conducted using SPSS and Excel software. The differences between the levels of the factors under investigation and their interactions were determined through analysis of variance, and the means were compared using Duncan's multiple range test at a 5% and 1% significance level ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physiological and yield component traits

The effect of soil salinity on physiological traits and yield components of different wheat genotypes in both regions was significant ($p < 0.05$). Comparison of mean data showed that the highest spike weight was obtained with 1.29 g in Miandoab, while the lowest (1.09 g) was observed in Rashkan (Table 3). The

average thousand-grain weight of genotypes in Miandoab (33.83 g) was higher than in Rashkan (29.12 g). One of the reasons for the decrease in spike weight and thousand-grain weight in Rashkan could be the high soil salinity of this region compared to Miandoab. Yadav et al. (2022) reported that salinity stress significantly reduces the thousand-grain weight of wheat, indicating a significant negative effect on grain growth and yield. In addition, Dixit and Chen (2010) showed that high levels of salinity, compared to low salinity, cause a 3.7% decrease in thousand-grain weight. This indicates that salinity reduces the number of grains and their weight, probably because spikelets are aborted during stress. Among the genotypes tested, the MS-89-13 genotype and the Alvand cultivar had the highest spike weight with an average of 1.40 g and 1.42 g, respectively, while the lowest spike weight was observed in the MS-89-10 genotype with 1.02 g (Table 3). Among the genotypes and cultivars studied, the MS-89-12 genotype had the highest thousand-grain weight with an average of 33.38 g. In contrast, the Zarrin and Alvand cultivars (without significant difference) had the lowest thousand-grain weight with 26.33 g (Table 3). The average grain per spike of genotypes in the Miandoab region was approximately 19.54% higher than that of Rashkan, with 24.98 grains per spike (Table 3). The difference between the highest and lowest grain numbers per spike among wheat genotypes was approximately 74.37%. The highest grain number per spike was observed in the Zarrin cultivar with 33.50, and the lowest number of this trait was observed in the MS-89-8 genotype with 20.17 grains per spike. Seddiq et al. (2021) reported that wheat genotypes with low leaf sodium accumulation under soil salinity stress showed better physiological responses to grain number due to increased sodium efflux. According to the results (Table 3), grain weight per spike under soil salinity stress in Rashkan (0.73 g) showed a 27.72% decrease compared to Miandoab (1.01 g). Merci et al. (2021) also examined the agronomic traits of wheat cultivars irrigated with saline water and observed a significant decrease in grain weight

per spike and grain yield with increasing salinity levels, with a significant decrease of 62.5% observed at the highest salinity level (9 dS m⁻¹). Saberi et al. (2013) also emphasized that grain weight plays a more important role in grain yield under salt stress compared to other traits among yield components. Narjesi et al. (2010) also showed that salinity affects grain yield and grain weight per spike. Among the genotypes studied in this experiment, Alvand had the highest spike grain weight (1.27 g), while MS-89-8 had the lowest with 0.72 g. Miandoab had a higher chlorophyll content with an average of 51.33 compared to Rashkan with 43.81 (Table 3). These findings were consistent with the findings of Turan et al. (2007). They reported that salt stress in wheat resulted in reduced plant growth, dry weight, and chlorophyll content, while increasing proline, sodium, chlorine,

phosphorus, zinc, and manganese values, indicating nutritional imbalance and stress-induced physiological responses. Conversely, Shtaia et al. (2019) showed that salt stress (up to 100 mM NaCl) did not have a significant effect on chlorophyll content in wheat seedlings despite a relative reduction in leaf water content. Volisevichi et al. (2023) showed that the duration of salt stress was the main determinant of the variability of chlorophyll content in wheat under salinity, accounting for 41.72% of this variation, followed by salinity level with 10.88% and cultivar with 7.63%. The studied wheat genotypes also showed a large variation in chlorophyll content, with a difference of 24.37% between the highest and lowest values. Genotypes MS-89-7 and MS-89-13 had the highest chlorophyll content (52.00), while Alvand had the lowest (33.39) among all the studied genotypes.

Table 3. The mean comparison of physiological and yield component traits of wheat genotypes under salinity stress at two different experimental sites

Treatments	Spike weight (g)	Thousand-grain weight (g)	Grains per spike	Grain weight per spike (g)	chlorophyll content
Experimental sites					
Miandoab	1.29 a	33.83 a	29.86 a	1.01 a	51.33 a
Rashkan	1.09 b	29.12 b	24.98 b	0.73 b	43.81 b
Genotypes and Cultivars					
MS-89- 4	1.34 ab	32.67 cde	29.0 bcd	1.11 abcd	48.33 ab
MS-89- 7	1.15 bc	36.33 abc	22.83 fg	0.98 cdef	52.00 a
MS-89- 8	1.06 c	30.83 def	20.17 g	0.72 g	47.00 ab
MS-89- 10	1.02 c	30.33 def	21.33 g	0.75 fg	48.50 ab
MS-89- 11	1.08 c	36.33 abc	21.17 g	0.87 efg	50.50 ab
MS-89- 12	1.26 abc	38.33 a	23.33 fg	0.02 bcde	50.50 ab
MS-89- 13	1.40 a	37.0 ab	26.0 def	1.10 abcd	52.00 a
Ofogh	1.14 bc	33.50 bcd	24.33 efg	0.93 def	50.33 ab
Pishgham	1.08 c	30.33 defg	28.50 cde	0.89 efg	49.17 ab
Zare	1.15 bc	28.50 efg	32.67 abc	0.94 def	45.83 bc
Mihan	1.24 abc	27.0 fg	33.0 ab	1.13 abcd	45.50 bc
Urum	1.22 abc	26.83fg	32.83 abc	1.14 abc	46.17 abc
Zarrin	1.14 bc	26.33g	33.50 a	1.17 ab	40.83 cd
Alvand	1.42 a	26.33g	35.17 a	1.27 a	39.33 d

In each column, the means that have the same lower-case letter (a, b, c, d, e, f, g^z) are not significantly different between the experimental sites or wheat genotypes treatments, based on DMRT at the 5% probability level.

3.2. Yield and agronomic traits

Experimental sites and genotypes had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on yield traits and harvest index. Harvest index (HI) was obtained at Rashkan and Miandoab experimental sites with 30.07% and 35.12%, respectively. The

difference between the two sites in this trait was 14.38%. Francois et al. (1986) reported that salt stress reduced wheat grain yield, straw yield, and harvest index. Furthermore, Kumar et al. (2014) showed that harvest index is a key selection criterion for improving wheat genotypes to improve yield under salt stress.

The mean harvest index of the studied genotypes varied in this experiment, and a difference of 22.08% was observed between the lowest and highest harvest index among genotypes and cultivars. The MS-89-13 genotypes had the highest harvest index with a harvest index of 38.5%, while the MS-89-8, MS-89-10, Alvand, and Zarrin genotypes had the lowest harvest index with averages of 30.33%, 30.17%, 30.67%, and 30.00%, respectively, without significant differences between them (Table 4). The average biological yield of wheat genotypes under salt stress conditions in Miandoab was 3378.33 kg ha⁻¹ and decreased to 2896.43 kg ha⁻¹ with increasing stress in Rashkan (Table 4, Figure 2). Therefore, the difference in biological yield between the two locations was approximately 14.26% (481.90 kg ha⁻¹). The genotypes and cultivars studied in this study also showed significant differences in biological yield, approximately. Among the genotypes studied, MS-89-13 had the highest (4633 kg ha⁻¹), and MS-89-8 and MS-89-10 genotypes had the lowest biological yield, with averages of 2527 kg ha⁻¹ and 2428 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. Therefore, MS-89-13 can be considered a genotype with high salt tolerance. Shafi et al. (2010) also showed that the biological yield of

wheat decreases with increasing salinity stress. Grain yield decreased by 13.81% under soil salinity stress in Rashkan compared to Miandoab (Figure 2, Table 4). Salinity stress inhibits plant growth and leads to poor crop productivity, negatively affecting wheat yield and yield components (Iqbal et al., 2018). Given that increasing soil salinity stress leads to a decrease in grain yield components such as grain per spike and grain weight per spike, the decrease in grain yield with salinity stress was not unexpected. James et al. (2011) also reported that durum wheat yield decreased by 50% under soil salinity conditions. Among the genotypes studied, the MS-89-13 genotype had the highest grain yield (2038 kg ha⁻¹), while the MS-89-8 and MS-89-10 genotypes showed the lowest grain yield with grain yields of 871.2 kg ha⁻¹ and 836.2 kg ha⁻¹, respectively (Table 4). Among the cultivars, the Ofogh cultivar showed the highest grain yield with 1421 kg ha⁻¹, and among genotypes, the MS-89-13 genotype (2038 kg ha⁻¹) showed the highest grain yield. Asgari et al. (2011) also showed that increasing salinity leads to a decrease in grain yield, while salt-tolerant genotypes such as Kohdasht (an Iranian wheat genotype) maintained higher yields due to lower sodium and chlorine accumulation.

Figure 2. The mean comparison of biological yield and grain yield of the studied wheat genotypes under soil salinity stress in the Miandoab and Rashakan experimental sites

Table 4. The mean comparison of yield and efficiency traits of wheat genotypes under salinity stress at two different experimental sites

Treatments	Harvest index (HI)	Biological yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
Experimental sites			
Miandoab	35.12 a	3378.33 a	1280.7 a
Rashakan	30.07 b	2896.43 b	1103.81 b
Genotypes and Cultivars			
MS-89- 4	35.17 abc	3701.00 bc	1500 bc
MS-89- 7	33.33 bcd	3417.00 bcd	1333 bcd
MS-89- 8	30.33 d	2527.00 e	871.2 f
MS-89- 10	30.17 d	2428.00 e	836.2 f
MS-89- 11	31.83 cd	2935.0 cde	1067.0 def
MS-89- 12	36.00 ab	3853.00 b	1605.0 b
MS-89- 13	38.5 a	4633.0 a	2038.0 a
Ofogh	34.00 bcd	3513.0 bcd	1421.0 bcd
Pishgham	31.33 cd	2789.0 de	999.2 def
Zare	31.67 cd	2787.0 de	1005.0 ef
Mihan	31.67 cd	2752.0 de	995.5 def
Urum	30.67 d	2696.0 de	946.00 ef
Zarrin	30.00 d	2740.0 de	936.5 ef
Alvand	31.67 cd	3154.0 bcde	1139.0 edef

In each column, the means that have the same lower-case letter (a, b, c, d, e, f, g[±]) are not significantly different between the experimental sites or wheat genotypes treatments, based on DMRT at the 5% probability level.

4. Conclusion

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the two locations and wheat genotypes in terms of the studied traits, and increasing soil salinity caused a decrease in all traits. According to the results, wheat genotype MS-89-13 was identified as a genotype tolerant to soil salinity in this study. Therefore, this genotype can be used to produce higher grain yield in saline soils. Among wheat cultivars, the Ofogh cultivar had higher grain yield under saline stress conditions, so cultivation of this cultivar in saline soils is recommended.

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